

The change of the proportion of seafood in Chinese diet since China's reform and opening-up and the forecast of the future trend

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Abstract

During 1978, China did its economic reform and opening-up. Ever since then, China's economy has been significantly improving as it opens more opportunities for them to facilitate various economic activities, and that also includes the aggravated proportion of seafood. We decided to do a comparative analysis of the proportion of seafood from the days after the reform, as well as the proportion of seafood from recent days, and what anticipation we got entering the future. We found that the demand for seafood in the Chinese diet is exponentially increasing yearly. This finding points to the increase in the proportion of seafood.

1. History on recent China seafood consumption

Seafood refers to plants and animals and their processed products obtained from oceans and inland waters, including fishes, crustaceans, mollusks, algae, aquatic mammals, etc. Seafood is not only an important source of protein for human beings, but also a food source with nutritional value and characteristic flavor, which has a vital impact on humans' health and their quality of life.

In the early stages of China's economic reform and opening-up (1980), the yearly consumption of aquatic products was already significantly substantial compared to other resources (e.g., milk, eggs) per capita, with it being 1 kg above both milk and eggs [1]. With the successful and continuous implementation of the reform and opening-up, China's economy has sustained development, and people's quality of life has consequently improved. The demand for healthy food such as seafood, which is high in protein and low in calories, has also gradually increased. In 2000, the yearly consumption of meat, milk, eggs, and aquatic products had drastically increased, with meat increasing from

294% to 47.3, while eggs increased from 516% to 15.4, milk increasing by about 567% to 6, and aquatic products increasing from 466% to 6 [2]. With the consumption of aquatic products vastly increasing, Chinese people's demand for protein-fish foods is on the rise.

China proposed a target of zero increase in aquatic products by 1999 in hope of coping with the decline of fishery resources. On the contrary, the quantity of aquatic products in 1999 was still 0.95 million tons higher compared with 2,356.72 tons in 1998 [3]. This demonstrates that the demand for seafood is continuously growing and is gradually taking a pivotal role in the diet structure of Chinese people. Nowadays, China has already become the world's largest producer and consumer of seafood, and seafood occupies an important position in the Chinese diet structure. With the reform and opening-up and the development of the economy and society, profound changes have taken place in the industrial structure, consumption structure, and the market pattern of China's seafood. At the same time, China is also facing challenges from resources, environment, international competition, etc. Therefore, it is of great theoretical and practical significance to study the changes in China's seafood consumption and its influencing factors as well as the market demand and supply of seafood in the future for promoting the sustainable development of the seafood industry, which ensures national food security and people's health.

2. The supply of seafood in China

With the increasing demand for seafood in the daily diet, there has been a significant increase in the quantity and quality of seafood supply. In 1980, China's total output of aquatic products was 3,899,600 tons, fishing was 3,122,100 tons, aquaculture was 777,500 tons, and pelagic fishery had not yet been absorbed [4]. However, after 2000, China's total output of aquatic products was 20,391 million tons, aquatic fishing was 11,894,300 tons, ocean fishing was

865,200 tons, and aquaculture was 9,279,600 tons, and the total output increased from 3,899,600 tons to 22,039,100 tons, an increase of about 465,163 or 1% [4]. According to statistics, marine aquaculture is in a state of continuous and rapid development, while the development of aquatic fishing is relatively slow and is continuing to grow.

China's ability to achieve this goal is largely driven by the following factors:

Policy encouragement

seven years after the reform and opening-up (1985), the CPC Central Committee and the State Council issued the "Directives on Relaxing Policies to Accelerate the Development of Aquaculture," aiming to accelerate the management, development and utilization of suitable fishery resources. establish a fishery development policy that focuses on aquaculture, fishing and processing simultaneously, and is actively promoting various ecological aquacultural models such as fish farming in rice fields [5]. China has liberalized the supply and sales of aquatic products, the market prices, the fishery management system, lowered the prices of fishing vessels to lower levels and made separate accounting, as well as confirming the rights of aquaculture water surface to households and contracted management, which has effectively aroused the enthusiasm for the development of fishery production. The active development of fisheries has promoted a sustainable, rapid and healthy development of China's fisheries and the economy of fishing areas. The implementation of this policy will undoubtedly effectively improve the enthusiasm of the fishery industry and promote the improvement of fishery science and technology.

Progress and development of fishery science and technology

In the early stage of China's reform (1980), the main source of seafood was aquatic fishing, accounting for about 80% of the total output of the sea. In 1981, there were only 845 aquatic vessels with more than 400 horsepower [1], but by 1999, there were 1,718 aquatic vessels with more than 600 horsepower. This shows the increase in quantity and quality of China's fishery production tools. Besides, China has also made great progress in breeding and aquaculture. In 1992, the number of shrimp seeds raised in China was 764.5545 million, scallop seeds were 778.1322 million, abalone seeds were 72.86 million, and kelp seeds were 13.21 billion beads.

By 2000, the production of fishes was 38,824,337 million, shrimp seeds was 58.367 million, scallop seeds was 175.32 million, abalone seed was 1029.57 million, kelp seeds was 15.532 billion, and laver seedlings was 217.7 million shells. It can be seen that from 1992 to 2000, the number of seaweed seeds was increased in 2000; hence, China's seed rearing technology made immense progress.

3. The early stage of reform and opening-up (1980)

In the early stage of reform and opening-up, mariculture and other aquaculture methods accounted for only about 20% of the total sea output. In 1981, the area of mariculture in China was 37,266 ha. While in 1999, the area of mariculture in China was 1,094,946 ha. From 1980 to 2000, China reached new heights both in terms of product demand and production. After the reform and opening-up (1978-2000), the proportion of seafood in the diet of the Chinese people continued to increase. After 2000, daily life of the Chinese people vastly changed. Not only did the deepening of reform and opening level up the overall economy, but also the level of modernization. Therefore, both the supply and demand of the Chinese fishery market were altered.

In 2000, the total value of aquaculture production is 42.7899 million tonnes, including 10.6128 million tonnes of marine culture products, 14.7745 million tonnes of marine fishery products and 223.32 tonnes of inland fishery products. Overall, the total value of aquaculture increased from the 20th century. By 2022, the total value of aquaculture production becomes 68.6591 million tonnes, including 55.6546 million tonnes of aquaculture products and 13.0045 million tonnes of fishery products. We can see that not only has the total value of aquaculture increased rapidly in these 20 years, but the proportion of aquaculture products is getting larger.

4. Changes in Chinese fishery industries-supply

To commence with, the quality of life highly increased in the 21st century. In 2023, the per capita GDP of China is almost 8 times higher than 2000(1). Due to the great step forward in people's lives, their eating structure changes. Having more income, people's choice of foods increased. They tend to reduce the intake of fat and carbs and have more protein. Therefore, fish has become more popular among Chinese people. Secondly, the process of globalization keeps propelling. After entering the WTO (World Trade Organization), China keeps propelling the globalization of the economy. By having more opportunities for traders to import and export products, both the production and demand for aquaculture products are increased in China.

While the fishery-related technologies develop quickly but are also in high demand, the Chinese government has decided to further boost the advancement in fishery technology development. According to the 13th Five-Year Plan and the 14th Five-Year Plan's fishery development plan, the contribution rate of scientific and technological development rose from 58% in 2017 to 63% in 2022. Overall, the technological level of Chinese aquaculture has highly propelled the development of aquaculture.

5. Changes in Chinese fishery industries-demand

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), from 2000 to 2024, there is a significant increase in China’s demand for fisheries, even taking into account the fisheries management measures implemented in many countries and regions [6].

First, global population growth affected the demand for fisheries. According to the United Nations Population Division [7], China’s population was about 1.3 billion in 2000 and is expected to reach more than 1.41 billion by 2022. [8] This population growth will lead to increased demand for food and protein, including from seafood and fishery products. Secondly, according to the FAO report and the Communist Party of China News Network - China’s Distant Water Fishery Development, the data of China’s capture fishery catch from 2000 to 2018 show a steady trend [8], but the trend of aquaculture is declining. This shows that even with challenges in resource management and marine protection, China’s fishing industry continues to grow to meet the demand for different kinds of seafood. In addition, with the rapid expansion of China’s economy, the demand for high-quality seafood and other fishery products in various regions of China has also increased significantly. This trend is having a significant impact on fishery demands as more people start to pursue higher quality food options. On the other hand, according to the FAO report [1], trade has also contributed to the growth of China’s fishing demand. It can import to meet its fishery product needs, especially when local seafood supplies cannot meet domestic demand. As a result, the volume of trade in fishery products is growing, which also reflects the rising demand for fishery products in China.

Overall, a wide range of data from 2000 to 2024 supports the view that China’s fishing demand is increasing [9]. Global population growth, demand driven by emerging markets, trade, and other factors have become important factors to promote the growth of China’s fishery demand.

6. Prediction on the trend of the proportion of seafood in China

This is a bar chart demonstrating the trend of Chinese residents’ consumption of seafood (Fig. 1). The brown line represents the average consumption of seafood containing algae, the dark blue bar indicates the consumption of seafood containing algae during that year, the green bar indicates the amount of other processed products consumed during that year, the blue bar indicates the consumption of algae during that year, the yellow bar indicates the consumption of Erbiu fish during that year, the grey bar indicates the fish meal processing dosage consumed during that year and the orange bar indicates the other losses of seafood. Statistics have shown that the amount of seafood

consumed by China has been continuously increasing year by year, and it is also expected that China will account for 38% of the global consumption of fish by 2030 [10]; this further implies that the consumption of seafood is only expected to increase in the future. One of the reasons for this tangible phenomenon is that the human population growth has been rapidly increasing (Fig. 2), which contributes to higher demand for food from humans.

图1 2013-2022年中国居民水产品食用消费情况

Figure 1. Bar chart of the consumption of seafood by Chinese residents during 2013-2022 [9]

Figure 2. Graph of the Human Population Growth from the early 1800s to 2022 [11]

7. The positive impact of the current proportion of seafood consumption

With the continuous improvement of people’s living standards in recent years, people have begun to pursue a healthy diet, not only to satisfy their appetite, but to pay more attention to balanced nutritional intake.

According to the scientific research report on Dietary Guidelines for Chinese Residents, the oriental healthy diet characterized by many fish and shrimp aquatic products can

reduce the occurrence of diseases such as obesity and diabetes, especially fish [12]. The report also mentioned that eating more fish can reduce the risk of all-cause death in adults. Compared with people who have never eaten fish, the total risk of death of people who eat 60 grams of fish a day is reduced by 12% [12]. Moreover, an appropriate increase in fish intake can reduce the risk of stroke in adults. For every 100 grams of fish intake per day, the risk of stroke is reduced by 14%.

Evidently, it can be shown that people will eat more aquatic products because they tend to pursue a healthy lifestyle.

8. Conclusion

According to our data collection in the past and present, as well as our expectations for future development, it is certain that the proportion of aquatic products in the dietary structure of the Chinese people is increasing, which is the general trend. The purpose of writing this article is to let everyone understand the development and prospects of China's fisheries, and to make predictions for the sustainable development of fisheries. In addition, we also hope to provide reference for other young researchers in need. We could expect that the growth of Chinese consumption of aquaculture products could keep rising in the recent few years. Together with the partially stable political situation over the world, the expanding aquaculture market of second and third tier cities, and the development of technology, it is expected that these factors can contribute more to the facilitation of aquaculture.

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